

STUDIES ON BASIC SULPHATES OF BIVALENT METALS (Cd, Cu, Zn)
PART II. COPPER

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The basic sulphates $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$ have been found to exist. In presence of excess of caustic soda solution the cuprate $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})_2$ is formed.

Various attempts have been made to study the basic sulphates of copper. Binder (*Compt. rend.*, 1934, 198, 653) from phase rule study has obtained the basic sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$. In support of his observation he has stated that X-ray examination also confirms his results. He has observed further that when copper sulphate is heated to 650° it gives the basic salt $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$ (*Ann. chim.*, 1936, 5, 337). Recently conductometric and potentiometric methods have been used by Chretien and Heubel (*Compt. rend.*, 1944, 219, 363) and Marie-Louise-Brouty (*Compt. rend.*, 1944, 218, 931) respectively to study the basic sulphate formation of copper. Both conductometric and potentiometric methods indicate the formation of the basic salt $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$ in conformity with the previous results. But the above two methods fail to give any indication of the formation of the basic salt $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$. Here thermometric titrations of copper sulphate with caustic soda and *vice-versa* have been employed to obtain definite indications about the formation of the different basic sulphates of copper. If the basic sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$ is found to exist and appear only in concentrated solutions then the analogy between Cu and Cd with respect to basic sulphate formation will be complete.

EXPERIMENTAL

The thermometric arrangement is the same as that has been described in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 157). Reagents used were of analar quality. Standard solutions of copper sulphate were prepared by direct weighing. Standard solutions of caustic soda were prepared by standardising with potassium biiodate using Wesslow as an indicator.

TABLE I

CuSO_4 soln. = 0.1M. NaOH soln. = 0.4768M. CuSO_4 soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 1).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	2.100°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.040	0.060	0.060
2	1.970	0.070	0.130
3	1.910	0.080	0.190
4	1.850	0.080	0.250
5	1.790	0.060	0.310
6	1.730	0.060	0.370
7	1.670	0.080	0.430
8	1.610	0.080	0.490
9	1.580	0.050	0.540
10	1.510	0.050	0.590
11	1.460	0.050	0.640
12	1.410	0.050	0.690
13	1.390	0.020	0.710
14	1.380	0.010	0.720
16	1.360	0.020	0.740
18	1.340	0.020	0.760
20	1.310	0.030	0.790

TABLE II

CuSO_4 soln. = 0.05M. NaOH soln. = 0.4768M. CuSO_4 soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 2).

NaOH added,	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	4.780°	0.000°	0.000°
1	4.705	0.055	0.055
2	4.640	0.065	0.120
3	4.575	0.065	0.185
4	4.510	0.065	0.250
5	4.450	0.060	0.310
6	4.400	0.050	0.360
7	4.365	0.035	0.395
8	4.340	0.025	0.420
9	4.330	0.010	0.430
10	4.310	0.020	0.450
12	4.280	0.030	0.480
14	4.240	0.040	0.520
16	4.220	0.020	0.540
18	4.190	0.030	0.570
20	4.170	0.020	0.590

FIG. 3

NaOH soln. = 0.17811M.
 CuSO_4 soln. = 0.04M, taken 40 c.c.

FIG. 4

NaOH soln. = 0.1018M.
 CuSO_4 soln. = 0.2M, taken 40 c.c.

TABLE III

CuSO_4 soln. = 0.04M. NaOH soln. = 0.17811M. CuSO_4 soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 3).

NaOH added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	5.320°	0.000°	0.000°
2	5.280	0.060	0.060
4	5.190	0.070	0.130
6	5.130	0.060	0.190
8	5.060	0.070	0.260
10	4.995	0.065	0.325
11	4.975	0.020	0.345
12	4.945	0.030	0.375
13	4.920	0.025	0.400
14	4.905	0.015	0.415
16	4.875	0.030	0.445
18	4.860	0.025	0.470
20	4.820	0.030	0.500
22	4.790	0.030	0.530
24	4.770	0.020	0.550

TABLE IV

CuSO_4 soln. = 0.2M. NaOH soln. = 0.1018M. NaOH soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 4).

CuSO_4 added.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
0 c.c.	3.010°	0.000°	0.000°
1	2.990	0.050	0.050
2	2.910	0.050	0.100
3	2.855	0.055	0.155
4	2.805	0.050	0.205
5	2.750	0.055	0.260
6	2.705	0.045	0.305
7	2.660	0.045	0.350
8	2.645	0.015	0.365
9	2.640	0.005	0.370
10	2.635	0.005	0.375
11	2.630	0.005	0.380
13	2.610	0.020	0.400
14	2.600	0.010	0.410
16	2.580	0.020	0.430
18	2.560	0.020	0.450
20	2.540	0.020	0.470
22	2.520	0.020	0.490
24	2.500	0.020	0.510
26	2.480	0.020	0.530
28	2.460	0.020	0.550
30	2.440	0.020	0.570

FIG. 5

NaOH soln. = 0.125M,
 CuSO_4 soln. = 0.25M, taken 40 c.c.

TABLE V

CuSO_4 soln. = 0.25M. NaOH soln. = 0.125M. NaOH soln. taken = 40 c.c. (Fig. 5).

CuSO ₄ added. 0 c.c.	Temp.	Rise in temp.	Total rise in temp.
1	3.380	0.000*	0.000*
2	3.300	0.080	0.080
3	3.240	0.060	0.140
4	3.180	0.060	0.200
5	3.100	0.080	0.280
6	3.050	0.050	0.330
7	2.990	0.060	0.390
8	2.960	0.030	0.420
9	2.940	0.020	0.440
10	2.930	0.010	0.450
11	2.920	0.010	0.460
12	2.900	0.020	0.480
13	2.880	0.020	0.500
	2.860	0.020	0.520

DISCUSSION

It appears from Figures 1 to 3 that the basic sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$ is formed when alkali is added to copper sulphate solution of strength (0.04M to 0.1M). But it is to be observed that only in the case of copper sulphate solution of 0.1M strength, the existence of the basic sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$ has been indicated. Thus it can be concluded that copper like cadmium gives basic sulphate $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$ at concentrations 0.04M to 0.1M. But at concentration 0.1M another basic salt $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot \text{CuO}$ is first formed which with more alkali passess to $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$. One peculiar fact is that no break in the curve corresponding to $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ is observed. This observation is in conformity with the conductometric results of Chretien and Heubel. The curves in Figs. 4 and 5, i.e., when copper sulphate solution is added to caustic soda solution, show that the cuprate $\text{NaCu}(\text{OH})_3$ is first formed which with more copper sulphate passes to $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$. But unlike conductometric method, no change of copper hydroxide to $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{CuO}$ has been observed here. McDowell and Johnston (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 2009) have also stated the existence of the cuprate ions $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_3^-$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_4^{2-}$ from solubility data.

Thus it is seen that in basic salt formation copper and cadmium show a very close similarity which may further be extended to other similar bivalent metals.

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